

ENVIRONMENTAL AND HEALTH DATABASES 2

Deliverable 2.2

Environmental and Health Databases 2

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.2

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
AKDN	Aga Khan Development Network
ALERT	Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CEDAP	Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (Italy)
CEpiP	Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (Wallonia, Belgium)
DEP-Lazio	Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
ERA5	The 5 th European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Reanalysis Product
EU	European Union
GISCO	Geographical Information System of the Commission
HDSS	Health and Demographic Surveillance Systems
HSS	Health Systems and Services (PAHO)
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LAC	Latin America and Caribbean region
LGA	Large for gestational age
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalised Difference Water Index
NoSQL	Not Only Structured Query Language (describes a type of database design)
PAHO	Pan American Health Organization
SIP-PLUS	Perinatal Information System
SGA	Small for gestational age
SPE	Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (Flanders, Belgium)
SPR	Swedish Population Registry (Sweden)
UGRAZ	University of Graz (Austria)
UNICEM	Unidad de Investigación Clínica y Epidemiológica Montevideo (Uruguay)
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index (a thermal comfort index)
VIDA	Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
WH	Women's, Maternal, Neonatal and Reproductive Health (PAHO)
Wits	University of the Witwatersrand
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This report describes the health, environmental and contextual data that HIGH Horizons uses to analyse the association between heat exposure and maternal and newborn health outcomes. It provides a second overview of the HIGH Horizons “environmental and health database”, in addition to the first report about the initial database (deliverable D2.1 [1]).

The HIGH Horizons database is not a single dataset combining all environmental and health data, but rather a decentralised repository of various country health data sources, and a central dataset with temperature data and heat metrics for the countries involved. This design ensures compliance with data protection regulations, upholds confidentiality and protects sensitive personal health information. The established health database consists of multiple datasets retrieved from national or district health registries or from hospital data. In comparison to the initial list of countries at the start of the HIGH Horizons project, the geographical scope was expanded and ranges from Europe (Belgium, Greece, Italy, Sweden) to Africa (Benin, Kenya, Malawi, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda) to the Latin American and Caribbean region (Argentina, Bolivia, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras and Uruguay). The environmental data used by HIGH Horizons are limited to data needed to calculate various heat stress indices, described below.

1.2 Relation to other project work

The database presented here informs the heat-health analyses carried out to evaluate the effect of heat on perinatal health outcomes. By using the same data

protocol [2], harmonised statistical approaches and data analysis scripts¹, we want to overcome challenges related to heterogeneity in exposure assessment, outcome definition, potential confounding and different statistical approaches, often observed in previous studies.

The data analysis findings are described in two deliverables:

- D2.3 Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 1, with preliminary results obtained during the first project year, up to November 2023 [3]
- D2.4 Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 2², due August 2025, with findings about the relationships between short-term (<7 days) and long-term (whole pregnancy) heat exposure on several perinatal health outcomes [4].

HIGH Horizons is committed to apply the Open Science principles by uploading project deliverables in trusted repositories (mainly in Zenodo) and by having our datasets "as open as possible, as closed as needed". The HIGH Horizons datasets (expected to become) publicly available or with restricted access are listed in the data management plan and related updates:

- D1.4 Data management plan (year 1), November 2023 [5]
- D1.5 Updated data management plan (year 2), August 2024 [6]
- D1.6 Updated data management plan (year 3), August 2025 [7].

¹ HIGH Horizons wishes to apply the Open Science criteria as much as possible and will therefore share the data analysis plan and scripts openly when the data analysis findings are published.

² Because the geographical scope has expanded, this deliverable title may be changed to "Multi-country analysis of the effects of heat on pregnancy and perinatal outcomes".

2 HIGH Horizons database

2.1 Database requirements and design

There are 3 main categories of data required in the HIGH Horizons project that can be grouped as: *Health, Environmental, and Contextual*. Previous research in the maternal, newborn and child health field has demonstrated that health outcomes are influenced by extreme heat (environmental), but this is modulated by contextual factors such as socio-economic status and age [8]. The main database requirements for HIGH Horizons are:

- Decentralised design within country storage so that sensitive data agreements are not violated;
- The storage of global environmental data that can be merged with the health data at country level;
- The storage of aggregated country data (health and contextual factors) where possible;
- Sharing of open data and data with data sharing agreements to facilitate analysis collaborations to explore indicators.

The database is in line with the original data management plan (deliverable D1.4; [5]) and related updates (deliverables D1.5 and D1.6). HIGH Horizons does not collect direct identifiers such as name or home address, only indirect identifiers such as date of birth. Due to data sensitivity and security, HIGH Horizons chose a decentralised database design similar to a NoSQL database for documents, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Entity relationship diagram between data holders of HIGH Horizons

Note: An entity relationship diagram between the different data holders with the need to analyse environmental-health data to come to a consensus on global heat health indicators for maternal and child health. 1..0 indicates that just that institute has access to the data, 1..1 indicates access is available with a data agreement, whilst 1..n indicates access across partners.

2.2 Health data

Health data considers all variables that indicate a certain medical outcome. Most of the health data used in HIGH Horizons is highly sensitive data. Where possible data is planned to be shared using data sharing agreements and spatial and temporal aggregation techniques. In comparison, where this is not possible, methodological sharing and the use of open-source software will allow for the robustness of methods to be consistent across partner organisations. It is felt that this is an important step in achieving one of the objectives of the HIGH Horizons project to identify global heat indicators for maternal, newborn and child health. Table 1 presents an overview of the health datasets or registries from multiple

countries used for the short-term and long-term data analyses mentioned above, followed by more details per country. The investigated health outcomes for both analyses are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 1. Overview of the health data included in the HIGH Horizons population analysis

Country/Region	Type of dataset	Time period	Data provider to the HIGH Horizons project
Europe			
Belgium	Birth registry	2012 - 2022	Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology, Flanders (Belgium)
Greece	Birth registry	1999 - 2021	University of Thessaly
Italy - Lazio Region	Certificate of delivery care registry	2001 - 2019	Department of Epidemiology of the Lazio Region Health Service, ASL Roma 1
Sweden	Birth registry	2014 - 2019	Karolinska Institutet
Africa			
Benin	Hospital data	2021 - 2023	The ALERT project*
Malawi	Hospital data	2021 - 2023	The ALERT project*
Mombasa, Kenya	Hospital data	2017 - 2022	Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa and UGRAZ
Soweto, South Africa	Sub-district registry	2017 - 2022	Wits VIDA (Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics)
Tanzania	Hospital data	2021 - 2023	The ALERT project*
Uganda	Hospital data	2021 - 2023	The ALERT project*
Latin America and the Caribbean			
Argentina	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
Bolivia	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
Ecuador	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
Guatemala	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
Honduras	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
The Dominican Republic	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network
Uruguay	Birth registry	2008 - 2022	PAHO/HSS/WH Maternal Network

Note: The Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity (ALERT) project is funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 programme. See references [10], [11] and [website](#) for more details.

2.2.1 Belgium

In Belgium, the declaration of every live birth—regardless of gestational age or birth weight—requires the completion of a mandatory statistical form (eBirth or Model I), which includes both medical and socio-demographic sections. For each stillbirth with a birth weight of at least 500 grams or a gestational age of at least 22 weeks, a separate statistical death form (Model IIID) must also be completed.

Healthcare providers attending births—whether in hospitals, at home, or in birthing centres—are responsible for submitting the birth declaration, which includes identifying information for both the mother and the child, to the civil registry of the municipality where the birth occurred. At the same time, they complete the statistical form containing the medical birth data. These pseudonymised data are transmitted, for births in Flanders, via the Flemish Government's Department for Care to the Study Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (SPE); for births in Wallonia, via the Walloon Agency for a Quality Life; and for births in Brussels, via the Brussels-Capital Health and Social Observatory—both to the Centre for Perinatal Epidemiology (CEpiP)—for further analysis.

In the context of the HIGH Horizons project, Ghent University (as project coordinator) and SPE signed an agreement under which SPE conducts the planned short-term and long-term analyses for all regions of Belgium, following the project's data analysis plan and predefined scripts. The merged CEpiP and SPE dataset covers the period from 2012 to 2022 and includes data on 1,285,495 births.

2.2.2 Greece

The national dataset from Greece includes 2 316 655 births between 1999 to 2021. Available outcome variables for each birth include i) live or stillbirth, ii) cause of stillbirth, iii) gestational age at birth, iv) birth weight (ordinal variable based on 500-

gram intervals). Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) is the owner of the data. Aggregated nationwide data on hospitalisations of pregnant women from 1999-2015 are also available. The dataset contains geographically aggregated data on hospitalisation per ICD code falling into the “Pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium” category (1999-2012: ICD-9, 2014-2015: ICD-10). Similarly, data on hospitalisations of children up to 1 year of age have been acquired. The frequencies of categorical variables and the means (Standard Deviation) and medians (min, max) of quantitative variables are presented in the first report on the environmental-health database [1].

2.2.3 Italy

The data used in HIGH Horizons is from the Lazio Certificate of Delivery Care Registry (CEDAP), which includes data on all births between 2001 and 2023 (of which data have been analysed until 2019) in the region, approximately 40,000 births per year. The Register collects data of all pregnancies occurred in the region, in both public and private hospitals. For each pregnancy, information is available on maternal, paternal and newborn characteristics, both individual-level and area-level. Furthermore, coordinates of the residential address (at the time of birth) are available.

2.2.4 Sweden

The data used in HIGH Horizons is from the Swedish Population Registry (SPR). The SPR covers 92% of all births in Sweden and it provides high-quality for research in pregnancy and early childhood. The SPR collects data on pregnancy and childbirth, starting at the first visit to antenatal care and ending at the follow-up visit to the antenatal care, which usually occurs at around 8–16 weeks postpartum. Approximately 621,134 singleton births from 2014 to 2019 were included in the dataset.

2.2.5 Kenya

The data for Kenya are recorded hospital birth data and were retrieved from the AKDN Delivery Tool under the Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa Surveillance Dashboard on a monthly timescale from 2017 through 2022. On average, there were about 650 births in the hospital each year. Following health outcomes are available low Apgar score (score below 7 at 5 min), stillbirth (death of the baby after 28 weeks prior to delivery), preterm birth (birth before 37 weeks), long duration of stay in hospital (>5 days in hospital), assisted vaginal deliveries, low birth weight (baby weighs <2500 g) and caesarean sections. A data sharing agreement was established between Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa and the University of Graz. Findings are published [9].

2.2.6 South Africa

The data used in HIGH Horizons is provided by the Vaccines and Infectious Diseases Analytics Research Unit of the University of the Witwatersrand (Wits VIDA). Wits VIDA funds and maintains a passive surveillance (birth register) dataset for the Soweto region of South Africa. Information is recorded on all deliveries at midwife-led clinics and a tertiary referral hospital in the region (N = 10). In total, 189,669 singleton births between 2016-2022 were included in analyses.

2.2.7 Sub-Saharan African region

HIGH Horizons uses data from the sub-Saharan African region, comprising 138,015 singleton births from a prospective observational study conducted in 16 hospitals across Benin, Malawi, Tanzania, and Uganda. These data were collected as part of the Action Leveraging Evidence to Reduce perinatal mortality and morbidity (ALERT) study [10, 11]. In this analysis, we included all mother-baby pairs admitted for childbirth in any of the hospitals between 1 July 2021 and 31 December 2023. We excluded mother-baby pairs who were referred to the

hospitals after giving birth. Data were entered daily by data clerks who were nurses or midwives in the maternity ward of each hospital.

2.2.8 Latin America and Caribbean region

The Women's, Maternal, Neonatal and Reproductive Health Unit under the Department of Health Systems and Services (HSS) at the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) coordinates a network of sentinel centres for maternal-perinatal health surveillance in Argentina, Bolivia, Ecuador, Guatemala, Honduras, the Dominican Republic and Uruguay. All the institutions use the Perinatal Information System (SIP-PLUS, for its acronym in Spanish) as a common data collection system. The SIP-PLUS database contains the data from the electronic perinatal medical records. The perinatal medical record registers health outcomes from the clinical follow-up during pregnancy. It records the obstetric history, information about the current pregnancy, of each antenatal care visit, information from labour and birth, neonatal and maternal outcomes, presence of maternal morbidity and information on maternal and child discharge.

2.3 Environmental data

2.3.1 Heat stress metrics

Unlike health data, there are fewer restrictions on environmental data due to the lack of sensitivity issues. While it was initially considered to rely on observational datasets from weather stations, reanalysis products were chosen because they are more compatible with geographically aggregated health data and allow the use of advanced heat metrics. The advantage of such metrics is that they tend to better describe the heat sensation and heat strain of a human body.

The heat metrics Air Temperature and Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) are based on ERA5 hourly reanalysis data from 2001 – 2022. This data, available from

Copernicus Climate Data Store at the hourly level and at a spatial resolution of 0.25x0.25 grid (approximately 25km x 25km), was aggregated up to the daily minimum, mean, and maximum (see Tables 3 and 4 for titled exposure). The reanalysis products of the heat metrics Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT), and Heat Index were provided to the project through a data sharing agreement. The definitions of the four heat metrics are given in Table 2 and are further detailed in the HIGH Horizons heat-health glossary [12].

Table 2. Definition and spatial and temporal resolution of heat metrics

Heat metric	Definition
Air temperature	The temperature of the atmosphere which represents the average kinetic energy of the molecular motion in a small region and is defined in terms of a standard or calibrated thermometer in thermal equilibrium with the air.
UTCI	The universal thermal climate index is a bioclimatological model of an average human body's response to different thermal conditions where the subject is not acclimatised to the climate and is outdoors, doing minimal work. It was developed as part of the European Cooperation in Scientific and Technical Research COST action 370 in the early 2000s. Most research uses a 6-order polynomial that is an approximation of a more complicated body model. The input variables are air temperature, dew point temperature, mean radiant temperature and wind speed.
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) is the most widely used heat index because it is an international standard for heat stress. Wet bulb globe temperature is calculated using observations from a wet bulb thermometer – a thermometer wrapped in a damp muslin cloth, a globe thermometer to measure incidence of radiation and a dry air thermometer. The equation for an outdoor WBGT is: $WBGT=0.7T_w+0.2T_g+0.1T_d$ The equation for an indoor WBGT is: $WBGT=0.7T_w+0.3T_g$ Where T_w is Wet Bulb Temperature (°C), T_g is Globe Temperature (°C) and T_d is air temperature (°C).
Heat index	An apparent temperature calculation designed to determine the temperature that the human body “feels” when its evaporative cooling mechanism (perspiration) is limited due to increased relative humidity. Heat index is determined by air temperature and relative humidity.

For the analyses these metrics were assigned to participants temporally (day of birth or trimester-specific) and spatially (coordinates of home, postal code, sub-district or facility of birth).

The use of environmental data in HIGH Horizons is not limited to Task 2.1 "Population-level effects: measurement and prediction" but is also necessary for the measurement of environmental exposures of health workers (Task 2.2; [13]) and for the selection of heat thresholds for the health risk alerts in the early warning system (Task 3.2; [14]).

2.3.2 Additional environmental data

As health data in Greece are aggregated at commune level, there was a need to create environmental datasets corresponding to the same administrative units as health data. The attribution of heat stress indices at the commune level (also referred as municipalities or municipal units), which is the lowest level of government within the organisational structure in Greece, enhances the usefulness of the data for statistical analysis against other parameters, such as epidemiological or socioeconomic data, which are often available at this level. The high spatial and temporal resolution of the data makes the dataset appropriate for analysis and comparison of climate change impacts, heatwave patterns, and the development of climate adaptation strategies at a regional scale in Greece. Moreover, the integration of additional environmental indicators, such as the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and various air pollutants, at the same scale facilitates investigation of the interactions between diverse environmental and heat-related factors and birth outcomes. Additionally, it can be used as a basis of a system to inform and devise targeted interventions and policies aimed at mitigating the effects of extreme heat events.

In addition to the environmental data described so far, the partner University of Thessaly collected additional data for Greece including various heat metrics, satellite data and air pollution. These data products are described in more detail in the annex.

The dataset integrates multiple environmental and climate indicators at the level of Greece's 326 communes over the study period:

- **Climate reanalysis (ERA5-Land):** Hourly data (2 m air temperature, relative humidity, 10 m wind speed) on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid were obtained via the Copernicus Climate Data Store API. Daily means were computed by aggregating hourly values. Using QGIS's native:zonalstatisticsfb, each raster band (one per day) was overlaid with commune polygons, and area-weighted mean values were extracted and exported daily to CSV.
- **Heat stress metrics:** Twelve indices were derived from ERA5 and ERA5-Land hourly data via the HiTiSEA scripts and the thermofeel library. Comprehensive methodological details are provided in Charvalis et al. [15]. Outputs on a 0.1° grid were aggregated across commune shapes in QGIS to yield daily mean, max, and min values for each metric over 9 131 days (Jan 1998–Dec 2022).
- **Vegetation and water indices (NDVI, NDWI; 1999–2022):** Monthly 32-day composites of Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 NDVI and the Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) were accessed in Google Earth Engine. For each commune, reduceRegion() computed the mean index at 1 km resolution, centred on the 15th of each month. A custom Python script then linearly interpolated these to a continuous daily series (gaps ≤ 1 month), producing daily NDVI/NDWI per commune.
- **Air pollutants (CAM5 reanalysis; 2013–2022):** Hourly concentrations of NO_2 , SO_2 , CO, O_3 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and PM_{10} on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid were retrieved via the

Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) ADS API for the rectangular geographic area enclosing Greece. Files were unzipped, and hourly values averaged to daily means. Using Python (netCDF4, xarray, rasterstats, geopandas), each day's raster was zonally aggregated over commune polygons to generate daily CSV outputs. Temporal coverage varies by pollutant, reflecting CAMS data availability.

For processing details, data specifications, and methodological notes, see Annex.

2.4 Contextual data

Similar restrictions to health data are present with contextual data, which includes factors such as socio-economic status of a mother or residential address. Therefore, sharing is only possible between institutes where the identity is completely anonymised. The factors of interest for the short-term and long-term analysis are presented in Tables 3 and 4 under the title Covariates. Again, the contextual data is described below for each country/region:

- **Belgium:** The birth register includes both medical and socio-demographic information. However, regarding residential address, only the municipality (postal code) of the mother's place of residence is available.
- **Greece:** The Greek national birth registry, maintained by the Hellenic Statistical Authority, includes anonymised data on maternal age, maternal nationality, marital status, municipality of residence (urban, semi-urban, rural), number of newborns per delivery, person present at birth, gestational age at birth, and mode of delivery (vaginal, caesarean, instrumental) for 2,316,655 births from 1999 to 2021. The exact municipality (commune) of maternal residence is recorded for every birth.
- **Italy:** Childbirth information and maternal sociodemographic characteristics are available in the Certificate of Delivery Care Registry. Record linkages with

Lazio Regional Hospital Information System and other registers provide data on residential address, other sociodemographic variables, and maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

- **Sweden:** The Register includes demographic, reproductive and maternal health data [16]. Everyone in Sweden has a unique identifier that allows for linking with the National Patient Register (for maternal and neonatal health outcomes) and Statistics Sweden for socio-economic and residential information [16].
- **Kenya:** The AKDN Delivery Tool under the Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa Surveillance Dashboard mentioned in section 2.2 did not record contextual data and consequently it was not possible to explore the influence of socio-economic characteristics on maternal and newborn health vulnerability [9].
- **South Africa:** Contextual information including past birth information, age of the mother, maternal HIV status, and infant sex are all contextual factors included in the South African data.
- **Sub-Saharan African region:** Contextual variables were abstracted by nurses or midwives from antenatal care cards (e.g., maternal age and HIV status), admission files (e.g., complications such as hypertensive disorders and antepartum bleeding), or clinical files (e.g., the baby's sex and birth weight), and were entered into the electronic REDCap perinatal e-registry form [17].
- **Latin America and Caribbean region:** The SIP-PLUS database mentioned in section 2.2 consists as well of individual data about the mother and the newborn. It records personal and family history information like maternal characteristics (e.g. age at delivery, parity, socioeconomic status, education level, body mass index, smoking), comorbidities (e.g. diabetes, HIV, chronic hypertension), infant characteristics (e.g. sex, birth weight categories).

3 HIGH Horizons data analyses

HIGH Horizons conducts two main analyses with the datasets described above: a short-term and long-term analysis of how heat exposure impacts perinatal health outcomes. The methods and findings of the short-term and long-term data analyses are presented in another project deliverable: D2.4 'Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 2' [4]. The variables used for the two analyses across the multiple countries are presented below.

3.1 Short-term heat exposure

This short-term data analysis explores the relationships between short-term heat exposure (the week before pregnancy) on three perinatal outcomes: preterm birth, still birth and APGAR score at 5 minutes. The analysis aims to find answers to the following questions:

- (1) What are the relationships between mean temperature and selected perinatal health outcomes within and between the various countries
- (2) Which of the four heat indicators (daily temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index) are associated with the selected perinatal health outcomes across the various countries, and can one exposure be adopted as 'standard' across all the settings?
- (3) Are the patterns of response different across different groups: e.g. mean annual temperature ($<21^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\geq 21^{\circ}\text{C}$), World Bank income classification groups, climate zones, seasons, maternal age and sex of infant?

The variables in Table 3 are used for all countries.

Table 3. Codebook for the short-term analysis

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
Health outcomes			
PTB	Preterm birth	Numeric	0 = No / 1 = Yes
APGAR	APGAR score at 5min < 7	Numeric	0 = No / 1 = Yes
SB	Still birth	Numeric	0 = No / 1 = Yes
Exposure			
MAX_TEMP_0	Maximum temperature on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_1	Maximum temperature one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_2	Maximum temperature two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_3	Maximum temperature three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_4	Maximum temperature four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_5	Maximum temperature five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_TEMP_6	Maximum temperature six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_0	Mean temperature on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_1	Mean temperature one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_2	Mean temperature two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_3	Mean temperature three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_4	Mean temperature four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_5	Mean temperature five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_TEMP_6	Mean temperature six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_0	Minimum temperature on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_1	Minimum temperature one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_2	Minimum temperature two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_3	Minimum temperature three days before the birth	Numeric	°C

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
MIN_TEMP_4	Minimum temperature four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_5	Minimum temperature five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_TEMP_6	Minimum temperature six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_0	Maximum WBGT on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_1	Maximum WBGT one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_2	Maximum WBGT two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_3	Maximum WBGT three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_4	Maximum WBGT four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_5	Maximum WBGT five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_WBGT_6	Maximum WBGT six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_0	Mean WBGT on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_1	Mean WBGT one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_2	Mean WBGT two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_3	Mean WBGT three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_4	Mean WBGT four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_5	Mean WBGT five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_WBGT_6	Mean WBGT six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_0	Minimum WBGT on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_1	Minimum WBGT one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_2	Minimum WBGT two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_3	Minimum WBGT three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_4	Minimum WBGT four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_5	Minimum WBGT five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_WBGT_6	Minimum WBGT six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_UTCI_0	Maximum UTCI on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_UTCI_1	Maximum UTCI one day before the birth	Numeric	°C

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
MAX_UTCI_2	Maximum UTCI two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_UTCI_3	Maximum UTCI three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_UTCI_4	Maximum UTCI four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_UTCI_5	Maximum UTCI five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_UTCI_6	Maximum UTCI six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_0	Mean UTCI on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_1	Mean UTCI one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_2	Mean UTCI two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_3	Mean UTCI three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_4	Mean UTCI four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_5	Mean UTCI five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MAX_HEAT_IND_6	Mean UTCI six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_0	Minimum UTCI on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_1	Minimum UTCI one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_2	Minimum UTCI two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_3	Minimum UTCI three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_4	Minimum UTCI four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_5	Minimum UTCI five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MEAN_HEAT_IND_6	Minimum UTCI six days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_0	Maximum Heat Index on day of the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_1	Maximum Heat Index one day before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_2	Maximum Heat Index two days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_3	Maximum Heat Index three days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_4	Maximum Heat Index four days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_5	Maximum Heat Index five days before the birth	Numeric	°C
MIN_HEAT_IND_6	Maximum Heat Index six days before the birth	Numeric	°C

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
Other			
PTID	Unique identifier for each person. Each PTID will have between 4 and 5 lines in the data frame (3-4 controls per outcome)	Factor	
I_SEX	Sex of the infant born	Factor	Female Male
M_AGE	Maternal age at time of birth	Factor	<25 = less than 25 years old; 25-35 = 25-35 years old; >35 = older than 35 years old
LATITUDE	Latitude of the location	Numeric	
LONGITUDE	Longitude of the location	Numeric	
CLIMATE_ZONE	Köppen-Geiger Climate Zone		

3.2 Long-term heat exposure

The aim of the long-term data analysis is to explore how multiple heat metrics (daily temperature, UTCI, WBGT, heat index), assessed by pregnancy trimester, affect various adverse birth outcomes including preterm birth, stillbirth, small for gestational age (SGA), large for gestational age (LGA) across multiple countries in Europe. The variables in Table 4 are for all countries, except for the covariates which depend on each cohort.

Table 4. Codebook for the long-term analysis

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
Health outcomes			
PTB	preterm birth: born before the completion of 37 weeks of pregnancy	Categorical	No; Yes
SB	stillbirth: die after 22 weeks of pregnancy, but before or during birth	Categorical	No; Yes
LBW	low birth weight: the weight at birth <2500g	Categorical	No; Yes
SGA	small for gestational age: below the 10th percentile (National Growth Reference)	Categorical	No; Yes

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
LGA	large for gestational age: above the 90th percentile (National Growth Reference)	Categorical	No; Yes
SGA1	small for gestational age: below the 10th percentile (WHO foetal growth chart)	Categorical	No; Yes
SGA2	small for gestational age: below the 10th percentile (WHO foetal growth chart)	Categorical	No; Yes
Exposure			
temp_mean_T1	Mean temperature in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_mean_T2	Mean temperature in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_mean_T3	Mean temperature in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_mean_T1	Mean UTCI in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_mean_T2	Mean UTCI in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_mean_T3	Mean UTCI in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_mean_T1	Mean WBGT in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_mean_T2	Mean WBGT in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_mean_T3	Mean WBGT in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_mean_T1	Mean heat index in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_mean_T2	Mean heat index in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_mean_T3	Mean heat index in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_min_T1	Average Minimum temperature in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_min_T2	Average Minimum temperature in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_min_T3	Average Minimum temperature in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_min_T1	Average Minimum UTCI in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_min_T2	Average Minimum UTCI in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_min_T3	Average Minimum UTCI in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_min_T1	Average Minimum WBGT in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_min_T2	Average Minimum WBGT in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_min_T3	Average Minimum WBGT in the third trimester	Numeric	°C

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
heatx_min_T1	Average Minimum heat index in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_min_T2	Average Minimum heat index in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_min_T3	Average Minimum heat index in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_max_T1	Average Maximum temperature in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_max_T2	Average Maximum temperature in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
temp_max_T3	Average Maximum temperature in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_max_T1	Average Maximum UTCI in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_max_T2	Average Maximum UTCI in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
utci_max_T3	Average Maximum UTCI in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_max_T1	Average Maximum WBGT in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_max_T2	Average Maximum WBGT in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
wbgt_max_T3	Average Maximum WBGT in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_max_T1	Average Maximum heat index in the first trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_max_T2	Average Maximum heat index in the second trimester	Numeric	°C
heatx_max_T3	Average Maximum heat index in the third trimester	Numeric	°C
Covariates			
sex	Sex of the child	Categorical	Male; Female
mat_age_cat	maternal age in years	Categorical	<=24; 25-34; >=35
bmi_cat	maternal body mass index (BMI)	Categorical	Underweight; Normal weight; Overweight; Obesity
meduc	maternal educational level	Categorical	Primary or lower; High school; University or higher

Variable	Description	Data type	Value
con_season	season of conception	Categorical	Winter; Spring; Summer; Fall
year_of_birth	year of birth	Numeric	
municipality	municipality code	Numeric	
geogr	geographic area	Categorical	North; Central; South
urban_rur	urbanicity	Categorical	Urban; Rural
county_code	county code	Numeric	
Other			
ID	ID of mothers	Numeric	ID
birth_date	Date of birth	Date	birth_date
gest_week	gestational age in weeks	Numeric	gest_week
gest_age_d	gestational age in days	Numeric	gest_age_d

4 Conclusion

This report describes the decentralised HIGH Horizons database and justifies the decentralised approach due to confidentiality of source data. The health and contextual data are sorted by the geographical area they cover in order to comply with national or district data protection regulations. By contrast, the environmental data consists of a central dataset containing all the temperature data and heat metrics for the participating countries, as well as additional environmental data at the national level.

The HIGH Horizons data analyses conducted with those datasets include a separate analysis assessing short-term exposure to environmental stressors as well as how long-term heat exposure impacts perinatal health outcomes. The variables used for the two analyses across the multiple countries are presented. Health outcomes were selected from a comprehensive list with common variables for all countries and prioritisation was informed by the update of a systematic review on the association between of heat exposure impacts on maternal, foetal and neonatal health [8], also conducted within the HIGH Horizons project. The

results of the two data analyses, which explore the effects of heat on pregnancy and perinatal outcomes, are presented in the deliverable D2.4 'Heat-health analysis report from Greek, Italian, Swedish and African data 2', which reports on more countries than initially planned. The geographical expansion includes Austria (about to be included and analysed), Belgium, and four respectively seven countries from Sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America and the Caribbean.

To incorporate health datasets from more countries and regions personal data protection regulations and varying methodological standards for data collection and reporting need to be addressed before getting access. Once the access is granted and the homogenisation and curation steps are completed, the analysis follows a preset scheme which makes the execution of the HIGH Horizons scripts quite simple. This uniform approach allows national and district health agencies to analyse the impact of heat exposure on their maternal and newborn health outcomes. HIGH Horizons has developed an analysis plan with accompanying scripts, provides these as a global good once the short-term and long-term heat exposure findings are published, and offers technical support to those interested in analysing their databases. Measures to facilitate multi-country analysis would include compliance with the agreements on health data reporting and applying Open Science principles.

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6 Annex: Acquisition and Pre-Processing of Environmental Data for Greece

Climate data: The Copernicus Climate Change Service includes in its products the ERA5 dataset produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). ERA5-Land contains the land component of the ERA5 climate reanalysis variables with an improved resolution of 9km (grid of 0.1° x 0.1°). The following climatic indicator variables were derived: temperature at 2 meters above surface, relative humidity, wind speed at 10 meters above surface in a netCDF (.nc) format.

Geospatial boundary data for Greek communes were downloaded in the shapefile (.shp) format from the Geographical Information System of the Commission (GISCO), which is a repository managed by Eurostat containing various geospatial data.

To assign daily means of the derived variables from ERA5-Land tiles over the Greek communes, we used a built in QGISfunction (native:zonalstatisticsfb) provided by QGIS (native c++), that calculates statistics of a raster layer (.nc) for each variable of an overlapping polygon vector layer. The zonal 'mean' value is weighted based on % of zone area that occupies a raster pixel(s).

For our case, a modified custom python script that utilised the QGIS function calculated mean zonal statistics provided a .nc file that every band represents a date measurement of ERA5-Land derived metrics, and the Greek commune's shapefile. The resultant zonal statistics were systematically exported to individual comma-separated values (.csv) files daily.

Heat Metrics: This dataset spans January 1998 through December 2022 and provides daily mean, maximum, and minimum values for twelve heat-stress metrics—Apparent Temperature (AT), Heat Index (HI), Humidex, Normal Effective

Temperature (NET), two versions of Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT and thermofeelWBGT), Wet-Bulb Temperature (WBT), Wind Chill Temperature (WCT), Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT), and both indoor and outdoor Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI)—aggregated at the level of Greece’s 326 communes. Hourly meteorological fields from the ECMWF’s ERA5 and ERA5-Land reanalyses (accessed via the Copernicus Climate Data Store API) were processed with open-source Python tools (including the HiTiSEA scripts [please add this ref <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-021-01010-w>] and the thermofeel library[<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101005>]) to compute each index on a 0.1°×0.1° grid. Commune boundaries from the Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT) shapefiles were then used within QGIS to spatially aggregate the resulting NetCDF outputs, yielding daily statistics (mean, max, min) for all metrics over 9,131 days. For comprehensive details, please refer to Charvalis et al. (2025)[<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.111264>]

LANDSAT NDVI and NDWI processing: Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) data were derived from the Landsat collection of U.S. Geological Survey datasets available in Google Earth Engine (GEE). Specifically, the Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 32-Day NDVI Composite and the Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 32-Day NDWI Composite. These datasets are constructed from orthorectified Landsat Level 2 scenes and represent the most recent valid observation for each pixel within a 32-day period. NDVI is calculated using the near-infrared (NIR) and red (R) spectral bands as $(NIR - R) / (NIR + R)$ indicating greenness intensity. NDWI is derived from the near-infrared (NIR) and shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands, typically around 1.24 μm , using the formula $(NIR - SWIR) / (NIR + SWIR)$, and is sensitive to vegetation liquid water content [18]. Both metrics are dimensionless and normalised to range from -1.0 to 1.0.

Greek administrative boundaries (communes) were imported as a vector FeatureCollection into GEE environment. For each commune, monthly average NDVI and NDWI values were calculated from 1999 to 2022. This was achieved by looping through each year and month, filtering the composite image collections accordingly, and using the reduceRegion() method to compute the mean pixel value within each polygon. The zonal statistics were computed at a spatial resolution of 1000 meters and exported as CSV tables to Google Drive. Each record included the unique commune identifier (KALCODE) and a monthly NDVI or NDWI value centred on the 15th day of each month.

To align these metrics temporally with other daily-resolution variables (e.g., ERA5), a final daily interpolation step was implemented using a custom Python script. The script created a continuous daily date range for the entire study period and applied linear interpolation for gaps up to one month. The final output was a CSV file with daily interpolated NDVI and NDWI values per commune at regional level from 15-1-1999 up to 15-12-2022.

Air pollutants (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service): CAMS European Air Quality Reanalysis dataset [19] were used to calculate daily commune-level concentrations for air quality indicators including:

- Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂)
- Sulphur dioxide (SO₂)
- Carbon monoxide (CO)
- Ozone (O₃)
- Particulate matter with diameter ≤2.5µm (PM_{2.5})
- Particulate matter with diameter ≤10µm (PM₁₀)

The dataset consists of model-validated hourly atmospheric composition data with high spatial resolution (grid of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$) over Europe. The Climate Data Store (CDS) Application Program Interface (API) is the service used to facilitate programmatic access for data retrieval.

The processing workflow started with acquisition of monthly .zip archives containing hourly NetCDF data for each pollutant. Those files were downloaded for the study period (due to the CAMS temporal coverage availability (2013-2023), all variables of interest were queried starting from 01-01-2013 up to 31-12-2022) using a scripted query to the CAMS ADS API. The spatial extent was limited to Greece (N: 42° , S: 35° , W: 19° , E: 29°), and data were retrieved for the “ensemble” model [20] at surface level (model level 0). For each variable, the archived NetCDF files were extracted, and hourly values were averaged to compute daily mean concentrations. The daily arrays were written into new NetCDF files (.nc) for each month, with an additional temporal concatenation step to output a full temporal sequence of daily mean values.

Using the official shapefile of Greek communes the concatenated NetCDF files were processed to extract zonal mean statistics per day and per commune. Each day was treated as a separate 2D raster layer (band), and mean values were calculated for all pixels intersecting each commune polygon. Zonal statistics were computed using the rasterstats library. For each pollutant variable, the resulting daily zonal means were stored in CSV format, indexed by commune and date. All scripts were developed in Python environment using libraries such as netCDF4, xarray, rasterio, geopandas, and rasterstats. The workflow was parallelised where feasible to improve performance given the large temporal extent.

Table 5 below summarises the temporal coverage of daily zonal statistics for each CAMS variable included in the analysis.

Table 5. Acquired air pollutant data for Greece

Variable	Start date	End date
Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	01-01-2013	31-12-2022
Sulphur dioxide (SO ₂)	01-01-2016	31-12-2022
Carbon monoxide (CO)	01-01-2016	31-12-2022
Ozone (O ₃)	01-01-2013	31-12-2022
Particulate matter ≤2.5 µm (PM _{2.5})	01-01-2013	31-12-2022
Particulate matter ≤10 µm (PM ₁₀)	01-01-2013	31-12-2022

The difference in start dates reflects the availability of validated reanalysis data per pollutant in the CAMS archive, with some variables (e.g., NO₂, PM, O₃) having longer historical coverage than others.